

A Review on Luciano Floridi's Philosophy of Information: Defense of the Dignity of Human and Call for Their Responsibility Inside Flat Ontology

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Technology expands our ways of thinking about things, expands our ways of doing things. [. . .] knowing a lot about the world and how it works. That's a major place where computers come in. They can help us to think.

Herbert Simon (2000), quoted in Floridi PI, p.26.

In the age of information, a philosopher challenged the audiences with the question, "now what?". One of his main debuts has been his ten-year work presented in 2011 and since then he has been a dominating figure in many discussions related to technology- artificial intelligence (AI) and ethics. The question was to draw human interest to the change that is caused by the great and rapid technological developments of our age. His call was first to make a conscious evaluation of the present situation and later to focus on the deeper questions related to ontology, epistemology, autonomy, ethics, reality, etc. I am talking about Luciano Floridi. Born in Rome in 1964, he had philosophy education in University La Sapienza in Rome. He later continued his education with MPhil and PhD in Warwick University. In addition to his academic positions, he also engaged with policy initiatives working together with the European Commission, the German Ethics Council, the House of Lords (UK) the Cabinet Office (UK), the Information Commissioner's Office (UK) and multinational corporations such as Cisco, Google, IBM, Microsoft. He is the founder director of the Digital Ethics Center at Yale University (DEC) (<https://dec.yale.edu>) and Research Group on the Philosophy of Information (IEG) at Oxford University (<https://www.cs.ox.ac.uk/activities/ieg/home.html>).

His lifetime project, *Principia Philosophiae Informationis*, -quoting his own words- is roughly in three quarters completed (<https://www.philosophyofinformation.net/about/>). The first book of this series is *The Philosophy of Information* (Oxford University Press, 2014), the second one is *The Ethics of Information* (Oxford University Press, 2013), the third one is *The Logic of Information-A Theory of Philosophy as Conceptual Design* (Oxford University Press, 2019) and the first part of the fourth one is *The Ethics of Artificial Intelligence- Principles, Challenges, and Opportunities* (Oxford University Press, 2023). Floridi defines the basic terms in *The Philosophy of Information* and gives the theoretical background for his theory while the second book, *The Ethics of Information*, moves to the more practical side of the project, the ethics.

Ethics, I would suggest, is an umbrella term for his comprehensive approach to most theoretical and practical problems circling around human-world-technology. His call is represented in what he calls philosophy of information (PI). From a collective text, Floridi published together with other scholars, we can derive the need for reassessment of our current situation and the background for this project/call: "The world is grasped by human minds through concepts: perception is necessarily mediated by concepts, as if they were the interfaces through which reality is experienced and interpreted. Concepts provide an understanding of surrounding realities and a means by which to apprehend them. Howe-

ver, the current conceptual toolbox is not fitted to address new ICT-related challenges and leads to negative projections about the future: we fear and reject what we fail to make sense of and give meaning to." (Manifestation, p.7).

The whole world he created in this philosophy is built on the term, *information*. Information plays a role like atoms play in ancient atomist theories, as it is the basic structure he makes his case in ontology, epistemology and ethics. This very much looks like a *first philosophy* and Floridi rightfully calls it so (*philosophia prima*) (The PI, p.24).

In Floridi's ambitious first philosophy, everything is framed with the atomic term, *information*. Despite his careful language to be inclusive, his first philosophy is far away from the pre-Kantian understanding of metaphysics: "This is why PI may be introduced as a *philosophia prima*, both in the Aristotelian sense of the primacy of its object, information, which PI claims to be a fundamental component in any environment, and in the Cartesian–Kantian sense of the primacy of its methodology and problems, since PI aspires to provide a most valuable, comprehensive approach to philosophical investigations." (PI, p. 25). That is because he focuses on ontological discussions and omits metaphysics (in its pre modern sense). The universe for this new frame is an *infosphere* (informational environments) and the agents are now *inforgs* (informational organisms). Floridi says he first coined *infosphere* in his 1999 work titled *Philosophy and Computing: An Introduction* (Ethics, p.6). *Infosphere* takes its inspiration from the term *biosphere* and it is an environment similar to cyberspace, yet more comprehensive from it (Ethics, p.6). It can be used within minimalist and semantic on the one hand, and maximalist and ontological denotations on the other. In its minimalist usage, it "denotes the whole informational environment constituted by all informational entities (thus including information agents as well), their properties, interactions, processes, and mutual relations." (Ethics, p. 6). And in its maximalist usage it is synonymous with being and reality. So now, reality is the totality of information, and the *infosphere* encompasses the physical, social, and cultural contexts in which information is produced, used, and communicated. This entails redefinition of the humans in their new reality/environment as they are no longer isolated beings in their knowledge processes and their data production capacity is shared by other agents. In the *infosphere*, human and other data-producing agents are interconnected informational entities, as *inforgs*.

I think this notion of *inforgs* is one of the most innovative dimensions of his proposal: we can now conceptualize AI and other similar topics brought out in the information age, in technological and digital developments that create a pseudo similarity to human beings and digital agents, machines, etc. Now we can talk about the issues that flattens their ontologies and erases borders between human and other beings without ignoring the inevitable ontological divides between humans and the others. For example (EX1) a simple act of calculation is done differently by a machine and the machine didn't really know but just calculate! However, the calculation can be performed by both the human and the machines. The background for the difference is well described by Floridi through the divorce between ability to perform a task successfully in view of a goal and any need to be intelligent to do so. This divorce made AI possible and also created the comprehensibility of the term, *inforg*. So the way AI works is different, its ontology is different and yet it is not intelligent. A calculating machine can not know just like a submarine does not 'swim'. This also allows us to create a space in this new ontology specific for humans. On the other hand, remembering *infosphere's* synonymy with reality, humans now start living in an environment created by and for digital entities: "I argued that human agents may know that they are neither zombies nor artificial agents, but conscious *inforgs*. However, as conscious *inforgs*, human agents share with other informational agents a reality made of information." (The PI, p.14).

I think this is also an important step in order to understand the new challenges in ethics. In a world, in which we are forced to an ethics without human beings, we can no longer continue the classical

frame where ethics is only applicable to the thinking/intelligent animal. We human beings were startled with issues brought to us through driverless cars, digital identities etc. The results of these technologies' actions are observable and physical. This is a brutal shift from classical ontologies, if we remember the very definition of extra-mental existence in medieval Islamic thought (Parıldar, 2020, p.59; Avicenna, 2005, p.24,25). Extra-mental realities are what causes effects. Accordingly, a mental image of fire couldn't but the extra-mental fire would burn. The digital age made digital realities cause effects and even challenge us by proposing alternative realities. Thus, our mirror to what is real is open to the effects of the digital. In this picture, the effect wasn't only through AI possessing autonomy but also it's shaping reality itself. Floridi mentions the fact that quite a large amount of data humans deal with is created by digital machines in this respect. The effects are tangibly real and in some cases their acts didn't really have individuals responsible for the action. Now with Floridi, we have a frame that allows us conceptualize ethical issues about these fluent individualities and ontologies and their responsibilities, and actions.

One other issue I want to mention on Floridi's revolutionary system is about reality and how the new era challenges us to review our understanding of reality. Especially the results of the digital revolution are impossible to ignore, but Floridi calls out all in power to act first, in terms of developing a sense of understanding the shift in our understanding of reality and second, a call to act as active agents directing the flow, in the digital revolution and not become passive consumers. Going back to EX1, the call for awareness is to the dangers of the dominant language becoming that of 0 and 1's, and that digitalization's risk to de-humanize the humans or reinterpret the human world for the human. This reminds me of an artist complaining online in a well shared tweet "I wanted AI to do my dishes so I could have time for my art work, not to do the art." A physical and objective world seems to be human beings' one and only escape to reality to defend the ontological safe haven of humanness. In Floridi's theory, human beings' uniqueness as being conscious, etc. is protected, yet he is careful to place humans together with the other beings in the world in terms of importance. So he continues the post-copernican aspect of humans' losing its central place and even the recent fashion of flat ontologies. This is a comprehensive ontological pluralism, in which Floridi also tries to make sure that we do not fall into the trap of relativism (pluralism without relativism) (Ethics, p.299; PI, p. 74). Floridi's description might present a case of human nature being reshaped in the digital age as well. I will only mention one example in this regard. He talks about re-ontologizing, digital divide and digital immigration. He claims that we are living in a world, data is mostly created by digital agents and as humans we are only immigrants in it. With the next generation of children the immigration to digital will be completed (Ethics, p.16). This separation of people living online and offline is called digital divide and it also calls attention to a digital discrimination of old age groups and disadvantaged social groups that have less or no access to digital opportunities and live mostly offline.

When looked at in its whole, I will summarize the main points that attracts my attention with my pre modern philosophy background:

1. Floridi's approach protects speciality of human understanding and its uniqueness
2. Additionally he maintains human ontology and ontology of biological beings separated from digital beings.
3. His evaluation of our new reality is well captured when he claims that there are things about machines that can perform acts that belonged to human alone in premodern
4. The end results of these mentioned in 3 might be impossible to differentiate but one should also be reminded of their separate ontologies and physical realities.
5. His words on digital divide and digital immigration and the data being produced more and more by digital agents, the presentation that we are more and more living in a world created by digital agents to be communicated by digital agents.

In sum, I find Floridi as one of the most impressive theoreticians of our age with his attention to theoretical detail and much needed strong construction (shall I call engineering) skills (Ethics, p.2) for the age we are living in. As the speed of change and its reality-shaping effects are inevitably upon us- humans, his call is a very important one for awareness and taking action to control the process in the digital revolution. One thing that makes this call critical is the uniqueness of digital revolution differentiating it from the earlier three revolutions, Copernican, Darwinian, and Freudian; that humans confront the danger of falling into the trap of being mere consumers in the rapidly changing world's new realities (Ethics, 14). Even when humans stop being active agents, the agency and authority does not disappear in this new reality, but becomes extremely open to misuse. Adding humans' inherent love for comfort to the picture, we can better grasp the need for urgent action. Understanding and evaluating the present situation requires hard work and collaboration of all levels of profession, and Floridi is one of the names to provide a basis for a common ground through information. In this framework, human dignity as well as authority and agency is secured together with an expanded ontology of inforgs in which human and non-human informational entities can be discussed in relation to each other. The mechanism of his conceptual engineering is impressive in its dynamic nature, avoiding non-foundationalist tendencies. He benefits from the metaphor of 'building the raft while swimming' (Manifesto, 22). This approach captures the need for a theoretical awareness of the situation despite the rapid change which does not allow for calmness and steadiness a classical theoretization process requires.

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